

INFLUENCE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ON PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING OF UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS IN PUBLIC UNIVERSITIES IN NORTH-CENTRAL NIGERIA

Gidado, Bello Kumo, Apeh, Hosea Abalaka and Diffang, Abel Dayo

Department of Educational Foundations, University of Abuja, Abuja, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT: This study explored influence of artificial intelligence on psychological well-being of undergraduate students in public universities in North-central Nigeria. six objectives, two research questions and four hypotheses guided the study. Descriptive and correlational survey research designs were employed for the study. The population of the study comprised of 234,650 full-time undergraduates' in all public universities in the study area. A sample of 384 undergraduates were selected for the study. A multi-stage sampling procedure which included, purposive sampling technique, simple random sampling technique and proportionate procedure were employed for the study. Two questionnaires which were validated by experts in the Faculty of Education, University of Abuja were used for data collection. The reliability of the questionnaires was determined using Cronbach Alpha statistics which yielded reliability indexes of 0.74 and 0.89. The data collected was analysed using mean score and standard deviation for research questions while hypotheses were tested using PPMCC, simple regression and Independent samples t-test. The findings amongst others revealed high extent of utilisation of artificial intelligence related tools for academic activities by undergraduate students in public universities in North-central Nigeria. The finding also indicated a significant relationship between artificial intelligence usage and psychological well-being of undergraduate students. It was recommended amongst others that, academics should monitor, educate and guide undergraduates on the proper utilisation of AI related tools and discourage its overreliance for academic related activities. Lecturers, parents and guardians should encourage students to limit or possibly avoid any screen ray be it laptop or android devices before bedtime, while also prioritising at least 7-8 hours' sleep at night among undergraduates in public universities in North-central Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

Since the manifestation of first generation technology which was electromechanical in nature hinged on vacuum tube. Technology has continued to witness boundless expansion and profound advancement through to the enormous fifth generation technology where robots are replacing and taken over peoples' jobs in some part of the globe. While artificial intelligence (AI) has become the fulcrum in almost every aspect of our everyday lives, including our educational environment. Innumerable artificial intelligent tools are employed for diverse

educational-related purposes by school administrators, teachers and students who are receptive and inclined to technological innovation. The technological-enhanced education forces brought about by a need for emergency remote teaching may have supported acceptance and readiness of emergent generative AI technologies (Crawford et al., 2024). Such generative AI technologies which may include narrow AI and reactive machine are fundamental components in addressing distinct academic related problems.

The advent of narrow AI and reactive machine which houses generative AI synonymous with educational related

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activities that are all essential components of AI technology and precursor of varied intelligent tools, systems and gadgets. Such as AI chatbot, Deep-seek, Nerd AI, Quillbot, Grammarly, Bing, Formative AI, Magic School AI, Perplexity, AI research and academic writing amongst others which could assist students address different academic related problems. According to Nwokorie and Onichakwe (2024), artificial intelligence tools such as ChatGPT, Scikit Learn, TensorFlow, PyTorch, CNTK, Caffe, Apache MXNet, Keras, OpenNN, AutoML, H2O, OpenAI, Grammarly, and Quillbox, provide learning materials that help students develop effective problem-solving strategies in their courses, provide students with personalized guidance, which help to improve their problem-solving skills over time.

Consequently, with the aid of some of these AI related tools, students can seamlessly write different academic reports while avoiding spelling errors and plagiarism, analyse large quantity of data within a short period of time, access relevant and related literature with ease, while learning could either be differentiated or individualised based on students' needs. AI algorithms can be used to create personalised learning plans for students based on their individual needs, interests, and abilities (Kelleher & Tierney, 2018). Other studies have shown that, AI improved individualised learning by adjusting to students' unique learning preferences and speeds, which improved cognitive growth (Aung et al., 2022; Ericsson & Johansson, 2023; Lin et al., 2024). AI also enables access to vast educational resources, promoting critical thinking and problem-solving skills (Rong et al., 2022; Williams et al., 2019). Rong et al. (2022) also emphasised that AI-powered educational games, simulations, and interactive learning platforms make learning more engaging and enjoyable for students.

However, due to the flexibility of AI related tools and its resourcefulness in addressing different human related challenges including education, students may likely demonstrate high reliance in solving diverse academic related tasks. Olarewaju et al. (2025) indicated that 49.1% of students predominantly use AI tools, while 64.5% demonstrated high reliance, highlighting AI's integration into academic routines. Also, Abbas et al. (2024)

highlighted that when students faced higher academic workload and time pressure, they were more likely to use ChatGPT. Irrespective of the fact that AI can aid a seamless educational process. There are questions emerging regarding AI to student relationship and how it impacts social connection, support, and belonging (Crawford et al., 2024). Overreliance on the utilisation of AI related tools by students has shown to be synonymous with AI dependency, difficulty in critical and reflective thinking or spelling of common words, cognitive overload, a shift in the sense of belonging from human connections to AI, anxiety, frustration, unlimited access to AI digital resources without guidance.

On the overreliance on AI related tools, Martin et al. (2024) emphasised that, concerns about cognitive overloading, reducing critical thinking, attentional biases, and overreliance on technology need to be addressed. Concerns are equally highlighted on how the overreliance on AI related tools could result to social withdrawal and addiction. Increased usage of unmonitored AI chatbots may result in adverse psychological effects such as social withdrawal, isolation, or AI addiction (Sepahpour, 2020). Lai et al. (2024) revealed that AI technology's implementation has negatively impacted students' emotional perception by neglecting care and respect and has led to a decrease in genuine interpersonal interactions between teachers and students. Excessive use of AI, such as misinformation, dependency, and technology addiction, which have a detrimental effect on students' mental and physical health (Chai et al., 2020; Ericsson & Johansson, 2023).

While Gopalan et al. (2021) indicated that university students display higher wellbeing when they have a greater sense of belonging, Gidado et al. (2025) revealed no significant relationship between AI Powered Chatbots usage and self-esteem among secondary school students. Turkle in Čekić (2024) also highlighted how virtual assistants and chatbots can induce feelings of isolation if users substitute real human interactions with digital contacts, which may exacerbate depressive symptoms. Alabdulkareem and Alzahrani (2022) revealed that the use of AI in digital communications can lead to heightened stress levels and a sense of overwhelm. These may all have

significant impact on psychological well-being of students which may include both male and female.

While some studies have shown slight variation on the influence of AI on psychological well-being, others have indicated no variation. Xia et al. (2022) revealed that gender moderated the association between AI knowledge and self-regulated learning such that the relation between AI and SRL was stronger among girls (RQ3, H3). Compared with boys, girls with stronger AI knowledge perceived greater satisfaction of the need for autonomy and competence, and girls with weaker AI knowledge perceived higher autonomy. On a contrary, Olarewaju et al. (2025) revealed in their study that gender analysis showed no significant difference in AI reliance ($p= 0.32$), suggesting universal adoption across demographics. Tanaka (2022) highlighted that female students and students with higher interdependent self-construal tended to be more motivated than male students. Also, female students have been shown to be more strongly influenced by the perception of computer self-efficacy, ease of use, and playfulness, whereas male students have been more influenced by perceived usefulness (Bao et al.; Ong & Lai.; Padilla-Meléndez et al.; in Xia et al., 2022). Other studies found that female students are more likely to experience anxiety and tend to be less interested in using technology for learning (Colley & Comber; Wang & Wang; in Xia et al., 2022).

Although the various researches highlighted above had explored AI's integration into academic routines among students in different part of Nigeria, little has been shown on their relative influence on psychological well-being of students. Despite the growing body of research on artificial intelligence and psychological well-being in different part of the globe, a significant gap exists in the literature regarding the Nigerian context, especially undergraduates in public universities in North-central Nigeria. Also, and based on the existing studies, it is evident that influence of artificial intelligence on psychological well-being remains unexplored. Which undoubtedly showcases the gap left to be enclosed. In lieu, it becomes imperative to investigate the influence of artificial intelligence on psychological well-being of undergraduate students in public universities in North-central Nigeria.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The increasing usage of AI powered tools among undergraduate students in public universities in North-central Nigeria is raising concerns on the potential impact it could have on psychological well-being. While artificial intelligence has become ubiquitous in modern educational environment revolutionising and transforming every aspect of teaching and learning and essential for students in simplifying some of their daily academic related activities. The role it plays in enhancing academic achievement is evident. This was stated in Gidado and Zubair (2025) who revealed a significant relationship between AI-ChatGPT and academic Achievement of undergraduates.

Irrespective of the importance inherent in the utilisation of AI technology, the researchers' experience with some students of public universities in North-central Nigeria indicates that, the overreliance on the utilisation of AI powered tools may lead to difficulty in critical thinking, over-dependence on AI technology, cognitive overload, heightened stress, shift in the sense of belonging from human connections to AI, social withdrawal and unlimited access to AI digital resources including irrelevant ones for non-educational related purposes. Which underscores the increasing influence of AI technology on psychological well-being especially amongst undergraduates.

In view of the foregoing, the research seeks to investigate the Influence of Artificial Intelligence on Psychological Well-Being of Undergraduate Students in Public Universities in North-central Nigeria, with a close focus on ascertaining the potential risk factors and protective mechanisms.

OBJECTIVES

- i. find out the extent to which undergraduate students in public universities in North-central Nigeria use artificial intelligence for academic activities;
- ii. determine the psychological well-being of undergraduate students in public universities in North-central, Nigeria;
- iii. ascertain the relationship between artificial intelligence usage and psychological well-being of

undergraduate students in public universities in North-central Nigeria;

iv. investigate the effect of artificial intelligence usage on psychological well-being of undergraduate students in public universities in North-central Nigeria;

v. examine the difference in the mean responses of male and female undergraduates on artificial intelligence in public universities in North-central Nigeria and

vi. examine the difference in the mean responses of male and female undergraduates psychological well-being in public universities in North-central Nigeria.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

(i) To what extent do undergraduate students in public universities in North-central Nigeria use artificial intelligence for academic activities?

(ii) What is the psychological well-being of undergraduate students in public universities in North-central, Nigeria?

HYPOTHESES

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between artificial intelligence usage and psychological well-being of undergraduate students in public universities in North-central Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant effect of artificial intelligence usage on psychological well-being of undergraduate students in public universities in North-central Nigeria.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female undergraduates on artificial intelligence in public universities in North-central Nigeria.

H₀₄: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female undergraduates on psychological well-being in public universities in North-central Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

Design

Descriptive survey research design and correlational survey research design was adopted for this study. According to Jongbo in Asenahabi (2019), descriptive survey research design involves a critical observation of events, objects, subjects and ideas without attempt to

control the condition of such phenomenal. This research design gathered information from respondents (students) during this study without influencing, alter or manipulating any variable. This method was employed for this study due to its appropriateness in ascertaining the opinions and views of individual respondents.

A correlational survey research design was also adopted for this study. According to Bhandari (2023), correlational design is the most adequate to be used when investigating relationships between variables without the researcher controlling or manipulating any of the variables. He further asserted that correlational design allows the researcher examine the extent of relationship that exist between the dependent and independent variables. Since part of the objectives of this study was to ascertain the relationship between artificial intelligence and psychological well-being. Correlational research design was very apt in providing insights on how the dependent and independent variables were associated without any manipulation.

Population

The population of this study consisted of all full-time undergraduate students in public universities in the six (6) States that make up North-central Nigeria (Benue, Kogi, Plateau, Nasarawa, Niger, Kwara and the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Abuja). According to data sourced from Nigerian University System Digest a subsidiary of National Universities Commission, the total number of regular undergraduate students' enrolment in the thirteen (13) public universities within North-central Nigeria comprised 234,650.

Sample Size

The sample size for this study consisted of 384 regular undergraduate students comprising both male and female which were sampled from different faculties and departments within public universities in North-central Nigeria. The sample size was determined based on Krecjie and Morgan (1970) table for determining sample size for specific population which was produced by Robert V. Krejcie and Daryle W. Morgan to help researchers address the existing gap of large study population.

Sampling Procedure

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A multistage sampling procedure was used to segment the population of the study into two phases in order to make the sampling process more pragmatic and explicit. At the first phase, purposive sampling technique was employed to select seven (7) universities from the thirteen (13) public universities in North-central Nigeria. One university from each of the six States including the FCT were selected for the study in order to ensure representativeness of all the states in North-central Nigeria including the FCT. The researcher listed out and wrote down all the thirteen (13) public universities in the six states including the FCT on a sheet of paper, after which the researcher purposively picked seven (7) universities, four (4) federal and three (3) states from the total number of universities in North-central Nigeria.

The second phase included a simple random sampling technique which was used to select the respondents from each of the seven public universities (7) participating in the study using Proportionate procedure to distribute the sampled universities and respondents evenly so as to achieve fair representation of the sampled students across the seven public universities selected for this study.

Instrumentation

Two research instruments were used in this study; which included one researcher structured questionnaire and one adapted questionnaire for collection of data. The purpose of the first researcher structured questionnaire was to enable the researcher find out the extent of artificial intelligence utilisation among undergraduate students in public universities in North-central Nigeria. The title of the questionnaire is; Artificial Intelligence Utilisation of Undergraduate Students Questionnaire (AIUQ). The questionnaire was divided into two sections; section (A) contained personal biodata of the students such as gender and name of university, section (B) encompassed 15 items on extent of artificial intelligence usage for academic activities by undergraduate students.

The second research instrument was an adapted questionnaire from Ryff (1995) with 18 items on Psychological Well-being which was modified for suitability based on the purpose of the study. While 8 items were subtracted from Ryff (1995)'s 18 item questionnaire, eight

extra items; from items 11 to 18 were added by the researcher to round up the instrument to 18 items. Also, the instrument was modified to a four-point modified Likert type rating scale. Ryff (1995)'s 18 items modified questionnaire enabled the researcher find out the psychological well-being of undergraduate students in public universities in North-central Nigeria.

To ensure the reliability of the items in the instruments after validation by experts in the University of Abuja, the instruments (two questionnaires) were pilot tested by the researcher using undergraduate students in the University of Ilorin who were not part of the main study. The two questionnaires had 40 copies each which were distributed among undergraduates within the university which is situated in North-central Nigeria. The test was aimed at determining if the items in the questionnaires were relevant for the study and also, if it could be used again for the same purpose. The data collected were subjected to Cronbach Alpha statistics to determine the internal consistency of the items in the instruments. The coefficient results of the analysis of the two questionnaires yielded reliability indexes of 0.74 for AIUQ and for 0.89 for RAPWQ.

Method of Data Analysis

The data obtained through the use of questionnaires were subjected to data analysis using appropriate statistical tools. Mean score and standard deviation were used to answer research questions. The research questions were graded based on a score of 2.50. which implies that, any item with a mean score of 2.50 and above were adjudged as "High Extent" or "Agree" while value below 2.50 were considered as "Low Extent" or "Disagree" depending on the questionnaire. The hypotheses were tested by the use of different inferential parametric statistical tools. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Co-efficient (r) (PPMCC) was used to test hypotheses 1. PPMCC is considered appropriate in determining the relationship or strength of the association between the means of two continuous groups of variables. Hypotheses 2 was tested using simple regression which is adequate for testing of effect of relationship between independent and dependent variables. Hypothesis 3 and 4 were tested using Independent samples t-test. Independent samples t-test is equally considered

suitable because it allows for the determination of the difference between the means of two groups of variables. All the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Research Question One: To what extent do undergraduate students in public universities in North-central Nigeria use artificial intelligence for academic activities?

RESULTS

Table 1: Extent of utilisation of artificial intelligence for academic activities by undergraduate students in public universities in North-central Nigeria

N=384

S/N	Statements	Mean	Std. Dev	Decision
1.	Utilisation of different AI technological tools such as AI ChatGPT, Deep-Seek, Grammarly, Bing, Formative AI, Perplexity amongst others	3.28	.701	High extent
2.	Usage of AI tutoring tools for learning and other educational purposes	3.20	.632	High extent
3.	Usage of AI technology to access educational resource materials	3.10	.620	High extent
4.	Usage of AI to write different academic related reports	2.96	.721	High extent
5.	Extent of AI encouragement in your academic engagement	2.94	.643	High extent
6.	Utilisation of AI technological tools to explore on different adventures that are not educationally inclined	2.61	.757	High extent
7.	Utilisation of AI powered tools to address academic related problems particularly ChatGPT	2.99	.638	High extent
8.	Extent of utilisation of AI in spelling of words	2.77	.680	High extent
9.	Extent of reliance on AI for most of your academic activities	2.77	.705	High extent
10.	Experiencing glitches using AI powered tools	2.32	.652	Low extent
11.	Difficulty to think on your own without the use of AI	2.57	.698	High extent
12.	Utilisation of AI algorithms to create personalised learning plans	2.78	.676	High extent
13.	Utilisation of AI in accessing relevant and related literature for your study or any research related endeavour	2.96	.714	High extent
14.	Utilisation of AI for data analysis	2.25	.661	Low extent
15.		2.24	.763	Low extent
		2.78	0.68	High Extent

Extent of doing your assignments or classwork without the use of AI

Sectional Mean/Std. Dev.

As shown in table 1, extent of utilisation of artificial intelligence for academic activities by undergraduate students in public universities in North-central Nigeria was presented. The table shows a sectional mean of 2.78, which indicated that over average of the respondents except for items 10, 14 and 15 which had low extent, all other items indicated high extent of the utilisation of AI for academic activities in public universities in North-central Nigeria.

This is in line with the decision rule that any value within 2.50 and above be adjudged as high extent and below be considered as low extent.

Research Question Two: What is the psychological well-being of undergraduate students in public universities in North-central, Nigeria?

Table 2: Psychological well-being of undergraduate students in public universities in North-central, Nigeria N=384

S/N	Statements	Mean	Std. Dev	Decision
1.	The demands of everyday life often get me	2.85	.670	Agree
2.	down	2.63	.581	Agree
3.	Maintaining close relationships has been			
	difficult and frustrating for me	2.64	.571	Agree
4.	I live life one day at a time and don't really			
	think about the future	2.58	.573	Agree
5.	In general, I feel I am in charge of the			
	situation in which I live I am good at			
	managing the responsibilities of daily life	2.62	.574	Agree
6.	I sometimes feel as if I've done all there is to			
	do in life	2.61	.540	Agree
7.	People would describe me as a giving person,			
	willing to share my time with others	2.62	.533	Agree
8.	I gave up trying to make big improvements or			
	changes in my life a long time ago	2.66	.511	Agree
9.	I tend to be influenced by people with strong			
	opinions	2.71	.577	Agree
10.	I have not experienced many warm and			
	trusting relationships with others	2.66	.542	Agree
11.	I have not experienced many warm and			
	trusting relationships with others	2.54	.556	Agree
12.	I do you feel anxious when using AI powered			
	tools	2.76	.516	Agree
13.	Sometimes I find it difficult to sleep at night			
	due to AI related activities	2.58	.555	Agree

14.	I do feel burn out due to my overreliance on AI related tools	2.60	.556	Agree
15.	I do experience feelings of heightened stress due to overreliance on AI related tools	2.66	.570	Agree
16.	I do feel depressed due to overuse of ChatGPT, Deep-seek and other AI related tools	2.61	.530	Agree
17.	Sometimes I find it difficult to think on my own, or even to spell out common words due to overreliance on AI technology	2.47	.545	Disagree
18.	Sometimes I feel stressed and depressed when encountering glitches using AI powered tools for academic activities	2.43	.522	Disagree
	Sometimes AI powered tools are error prone and biased especially Chabot's' ChatGPT which results to frustration	2.77	0.56	Agree
Sectional Mean/Std. Dev.				

As shown in table 2, the psychological well-being of undergraduate students in public universities in North-central, Nigeria was presented. The table shows a sectional mean of 2.77, which indicated that over average of the respondents except for items 17 and 18 who disagreed, all agreed on the items on psychological well-being of undergraduate students in public universities in North-central, Nigeria. This is in line with the decision rule that

any value within 2.50 and above be adjudged as agree and below be considered as disagree.

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between artificial intelligence usage and psychological well-being of undergraduate students in public universities in North-central Nigeria.

Table 3: Correlation Test between Artificial Intelligence usage and Psychological Well-being of Undergraduate Students in North-central Nigeria

Variables	N	\bar{X}	SD	r-cal	p-value	Decision
Artificial Intelligence and Psychological Well-being	384	2.80	.22	.152**	.003	Significant

Correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2-tailed) PPMC As shown in table 3, PPMC correlation test between artificial intelligence usage and psychological well-being of undergraduate students in public universities in North-central, Nigeria was presented. The table indicated a positive value of 'r' which points to direction of relationship between AI usage and psychological well-

being. Showing that increase in one variable corresponds to increase in the other. The significant value of .003 which is less than 0.05 level of significance indicates a significant relationship between AI usage and psychological well-being of undergraduate students. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected.

Table 4: Simple Regression Analysis on effect of Artificial Intelligence on Psychological Well-being of Undergraduate Students in public universities in North-central Nigeria

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	2.287	.122		18.761	.000
Artificial Intelligence	.144	.089	.178	1.615	.107

(F (4, 537) = p < .011)

a. Dependent Variable: Psychological Well-being

As shown in table 4, the coefficients of simple regression analysis on the effect of artificial intelligence on psychological well-being of undergraduate students in public universities in North-central Nigeria was presented. The table shows an unstandardized coefficient (B = .144, p > .107) which signifies that AI have a significant negative effect on Psychological well-being. This implies that for

every one-unit increase in utilisation of AI technology psychological well-being decreases by .144 and -.024 units respectively. The variance in AI ($R^2 = .023$) with a significant F-statistic (**F (4, 537) = p < .011**) which indicates that AI could affect psychological well-being of undergraduate students. This infers that there is significant effect of AI on psychological well-being of undergraduate students in public universities in North-central Nigeria.

Table 5: Independent Samples t-test Analysis on Mean responses of Male and Female Undergraduates on Artificial Intelligence in Public Universities in North-central Nigeria

Variables	Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	t-value	Df	Sig(2tailed)	Decision
Artificial Intelligence	Male	205	2.80	0.21	-.409	382	.683	Not Rejected
	Female	179	2.81	0.23				

As shown in table 5, an independent samples t-test analysis on the mean responses of male and female undergraduates on artificial intelligence in public universities in North-central Nigeria was presented. The table reveals a means of 2.80 and SD of 0.21 for male while means of 2.81 and SD of 0.23 for female on AI responses with a t-value of -

.409 and .683 p > 0.05. This infers that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female undergraduates on artificial intelligence in public universities in North-central Nigeria. The hypothesis is therefore not rejected (retained).

Table 6: Independent Samples t-test Analysis on Mean responses of Male and Female Undergraduates on Psychological Well-being in Public Universities in North-central Nigeria

Variables	Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	t-value	Df	Sig(2tailed)	Decision
Psychological Well-being	Male	205	2.63	0.17	.961	382	.337	Not Rejected
	Female	179	2.61	0.19				

As shown in table 6, an independent samples t-test analysis on the mean responses of male and female undergraduates on psychological well-being in public universities in North-central Nigeria was presented. The table reveals a means of 2.63 and SD of 0.17 for male while means of 2.61 and SD of 0.19 for female with a t-value .961 and .337 $p > 0.05$. This infers that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female undergraduates on psychological well-being in public universities in North-central Nigeria. The hypothesis is therefore not rejected (retained).

DISCUSSIONS

Findings from this study indicated high extent in the utilisation of artificial intelligence related tools for academic activities by undergraduate students in public universities in North-central Nigeria. This is corroborated by Olarewaju et al. (2025) whose findings indicated that 49.1% of students predominantly use AI tools, while 64.5% demonstrated high reliance, highlighting AI's integration into academic routines. Abbas et al. (2024)'s findings is partly in variance with present finding since they highlighted that when students faced higher academic workload and time pressure, they were more likely to use ChatGPT. In contrast, students who were sensitive to rewards were less likely to use ChatGPT. Nevertheless, Nwokorie and Onichakwe (2024) supported this finding since their findings revealed that, artificial intelligence tools such as ChatGPT, Scikit Learn, TensorFlow, PyTorch, CNTK, Caffe, Apache MXNet, Keras, OpenNN, AutoML, H2O, OpenAI, Grammarly, and Quillbox, provide learning materials that help students develop effective problem-solving strategies in their courses, provide students with personalized guidance, which help to improve their problem-solving skills over time.

The findings also revealed that demands of everyday life, difficulty to sleep at night due to excessive use of social media amongst others were some of the contributing factors of psychological well-being of undergraduate students in public universities in North-central, Nigeria. Social media has become an integral part of teenagers' lives, providing platforms for socializing, self-expression, and information sharing (Bankawat, 2024). He continued

that, although it encourages creativity and connection, excessive usage can result in addiction, sleep disturbances, and mental health issues such as anxiety and depression. Being on social media for more than 5 hours a day was linked to sleep disorders, memory impairment, and learning disabilities (Scott et al., 2019). However, Burke and Kraut (2016) found that general Facebook communication was not associated with changes in psychological well-being over three months. They indicated that receiving communication from strong ties was related with higher well-being however, communication from weak ties was not related with psychological well-being.

The findings equally indicated a significant relationship between artificial intelligence usage and psychological well-being of undergraduate students. This finding is in variance with Gidado et al. (2025) who revealed that there was no significant relationship between AI Powered Chatbots usage and self-esteem. However, Lai et al. (2024) revealed that AI technology's implementation has negatively impacted students' emotional perception by neglecting care and respect and has led to a decrease in genuine interpersonal interactions between teachers and students. Excessive use of AI, such as misinformation, dependency, and technology addiction, which have a detrimental effect on students' mental and physical health (Chai et al., 2020; Ericsson & Johansson, 2023).

The findings further signposted a significant effect in the relationship among AI, SM utilisation and psychological well-being of undergraduate students. This in line with Turkle in Ćekić (2024) who revealed how virtual assistants and chatbots can induce feelings of isolation if users substitute real human interactions with digital contacts, which may exacerbate depressive symptoms. Also in a related finding, Alabdulkareem and Alzahrani (2022) revealed that the use of AI in digital communications can lead to heightened stress levels and a sense of overwhelm. On the effect of SM on psychological well-being, Anwar et al. (2022) indicated significant positive correlation between social media usage and academic procrastination. While Bibire (2020) also showed a significant effect of social networking sites usage on undergraduates' Psychological well-being. Olola et al. (2022) also revealed

a significant effect of the use of social media on the psychological wellbeing of the students in Minnesota, United States of America. However, Ostic et al. (2021) findings point to an overall positive indirect impact of social media usage on psychological well-being.

The findings also revealed that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female undergraduates on artificial intelligence, social media utilisation, psychological well-being and academic procrastination in public universities in North-central Nigeria. This is in line with Olarewaju et al. (2025) who revealed in their study that gender analysis showed no significant difference in AI reliance ($p= 0.32$), suggesting universal adoption across demographics. On a contrary, Xia et al. (2022) revealed that gender moderated the association between AI knowledge and self-regulated learning such that the relation between AI and SRL was stronger among girls (RQ3, H3). Compared with boys, girls with stronger AI knowledge perceived greater satisfaction of the need for autonomy and competence, and girls with weaker AI knowledge perceived higher autonomy. On social media, females demonstrated a stronger correlation for heavy social networking (two hours or greater) and increased anxiety symptoms, but smaller correlation between the two for males (Mundy et al., 2020). While Keles et al. (2019) indicated that females showed a significantly higher correlation between social media use, body shaming, and social physique anxiety than male adolescents. On psychological well-being, Sahoo et al. (2024) revealed that the psychological well-being scores of the boys ($M = 69.73$) had higher than girls ($M = 64.10$) subjects, indicating that boys had greater psychological wellness and were psychologically healthier than their girl counterparts. On procrastination, Touloupis and Campbell (2023) revealed that no gender differences were found regarding students' procrastination. Some studies posited that male university students tend to procrastinate to a greater extent compared to females (Balkis & Erdinç, 2017; Khan et al. in Touloupis & Campbell, 2023), while others reveal females' over-representation in this behaviour (Ghosh & Roy, 2017; Özer et al. in Touloupis & Campbell, 2023), while other scholars proclaim that there is no significant gender-based

difference in academic procrastination (Ajayi, 2020; Amoke et al., 2021; He, 2017).

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that AI has multifaceted significance in the educational environment if judiciously utilised. The study has shown how AI is pertinent in assisting students to address different human related challenges, educational inclusive. Hence, AI tools such as ChatGPT, Deep-Seek, Grammarly, Bing, Formative AI, Perplexity amongst others could be used for tutorials, learning, accessing educational resource materials, writing of different academic related reports and other educational purposes.

However, the overreliance on some of these AI technology related tools have equally shown to have significant impact on psychological well-being irrespective of gender of undergraduate students in public universities in North-central Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Academics should monitor, educate and guide undergraduates on the proper utilisation of AI related tools and discourage its overreliance for academic related activities.
2. Lecturers, parents and guardians should encourage students to limit or possibly avoid any screen ray be it laptop or android devices before bedtime, while also prioritising at least 7-8 hours' sleep at night.
3. University administrators, academics, parents and community leaders should encourage community-based programmes, wide-discussions on mental health and well-being.
4. Parents and academics should discourage students from overreliance on AI tools, and also ensure students with psychological related issues seek professional psychological help to enhance their psychological well-being.
5. Academics should monitor, educate and guide undergraduates on the proper utilisation of AI related tools and discourage its overreliance for academic related activities regardless of gender.

6. Academics, parents and guardians should prioritise raising awareness among students on the potential hazards associated with excessive dependence on AI related tools on psychological well-being regardless of gender.

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